

AS26556, a high-yielding red rice for semidry conditions

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In Kanyakumari district, Thovazhai and Agastheeswaram taluks have 7,000 ha of land under semidry cropping. They do not get sufficient rainfall during May-June and, because they are tail-end areas, irrigation water is generally delayed.

Rice is direct seeded when summer rains start. Local consumers prefer short bold red rice. We tested six red rice and one white rice entries under semidry conditions during the 1986 and 1987 wet seasons. The soil was a Typic Hapludalf. Rainfall received during crop growth is given in Table 1. Plot size was 4 × 2 m. Seeds were dibbled at 3-4/hill with 20 × 10-cm spacing in a randomized block design with 3 replications. Sowing dates were 27 May 1986 and 23 May 1987.

AS26556 (IET5233/IR2153-26-3-5-2) had the highest yield (average 2.8 t/ha in 109 d) (Table 2). Its grain is a bold red rice. It has high panicle weight and low sterility. □

Table 1. Rainfall amount and distribution during crop growth. Tamil Nadu, India, 1986-87.

Month	1986 wet season ^a		1987 wet season ^b		10 yr av rainfall (mm)
	Rainfall (mm)	Rainy days (no.)	Rainfall (mm)	Rainy days (no.)	
May	—	—	12.0	1	161
Jun	17.0	2	17.0	1	293
Jul	20.5	3	9.9	2	129
Aug	123.0	7	56.2	4	95
Sep	18.2	3	—	—	121
Total	178.7	15	95.1	8	798

^a Sowing on 27 May 1986, harvest on 18 Sep. ^b Sowing on 23 May 1987, harvest on 12 Sep.

Table 2. Performance of 7 varieties under semidry condition at Agricultural Research Station, Tirupathisaram - 629901, India. 1986 and 1987 kharif.

Culture	Grain yield (t/ha)			Duration (d)	Panicles (no./hill)	Panicle weight (g)	1000-grain weight (g)	Sterility (%)	Rice color
	1986	1987	Mean						
AS26556	2.9	2.7	2.8	109	8.0	1.4	24.2	12.8	Red
TP5106	2.8	1.8	2.3	105	10.0	0.9	21.5	17.2	Red
AS24913	2.4	1.8	2.1	112	9.0	1.3	19.6	14.4	Red
TM8089	2.8	1.4	2.1	105	9.0	1.2	24.0	13.5	Red
TKM9	1.8	2.0	1.9	105	8.0	1.1	24.1	13.7	Red
AS22954	1.7	1.5	1.6	109	9.0	1.0	26.9	15.1	Red
BG367-4	1.7	0.7	1.2	112	7.0	1.0	19.7	14.1	White
LSD (P=0.05)	0.3	0.4		3	0.9	0.2	2.7	1.4	

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Adverse soils tolerance

Path analysis of rice grain yield under saline conditions

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Rice production in saline soils could be increased considerably if salt-tolerant varieties were developed. We studied the association between yield components and grain yield under saline conditions to identify the characters that contribute to yield.

Seedlings of 19 promising lines from 7 crosses involving salt-tolerant parents were transplanted at 25 d after seeding (DAS) in a lowland field in Binh Dai

District, Mekong Delta during 1987 wet season.

Spacing was 15 × 20 cm in a randomized complete block design with 3 replications. Fertilizer was applied at 80-0-0 kg NPK/ha. Soil was silty clay with EC_e = 11.8 dS/m before

transplanting and 2.8 dS/m at flowering. Path coefficient analysis was used to partition the genotypic correlation coefficient into direct and indirect effects.

Under saline conditions, filled grains per panicle had the largest direct effect on yield (1.092) (see table). However, its effect through sterility percentage was negative (-0.375), even though the total correlation with yield was significant.

Path analysis showing direct and indirect effects of yield components on yield.^a Haugiang, Vietnam.

Variable	Panicles/m ²	Panicle length	Filled grains/panicle	Sterility percentage	1000-grain weight	Total genotypic correlation with yield
Panicle/m ²	-0.191 ^b	-0.248	-0.203	0.378	0.055	-0.209
Panicle length	-0.091	0.523 ^b	0.186	0.287	-0.054	-0.195
Filled grains/panicle	0.036	-0.089	1.092 ^b	-0.375	-0.069	0.595
Sterility percentage	-0.078	-0.162	-0.441	-0.928 ^b	-0.033	0.215
1000-grain weight	0.045	-0.121	0.320	0.130	-0.234 ^b	0.140

^a Residual effect = 0.204. ^b Direct effects. All others are indirect effects.